

GLOBALIZATION AND GROWTH OF EMERGING ECONOMIES: LESSONS FROM BANGLADESH

DR. MD. SHAH ALAM

shahmdalam@ru.edu.bd

Department of Accounting and Information Systems

University of Rajshahi

Rajshahi-6205, Bangladesh

ABSTRACT

The paper aims at presenting the globalization and economic growth of the emerging countries along with the lessons of Bangladesh. The term globalization insists on the process through which the economy of the world becomes increasingly integrated in order to lead a global economy and economic policy making. It also provides facilities to the growth of emerging economies. The paper also covers the developmental aspects of Bangladesh economy. To conduct the study, secondary data have been used. During conducting the study, it is clarified that globalization has created facilities for the growth of the economies of the emerging countries. It is found that many emerging countries in the world has developed their economies tremendously. Following the development, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh has liberalized her investment policy, fiscal policies to create conducive environment in order to attract foreign investors for investment into Bangladesh with a view to accelerating economic growth.

Keywords: Globalization, Emerging economies, Investment policy, Factors of production, Economic emancipation, Foreign Direct Investment